

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MEDIA VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: In the modern context of the formation of the information society, the study of the language of the media is of particular importance. If until recently the activity of language in the field of media was studied by different branches of linguistics - sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, etc., now there are all the conditions to unite all the research. In this article we will consider the comparative study of the language of mass media in English and Uzbek in the framework of one special discipline - media linguistics.

Keywords: media linguistics, media, media texts, ICT, print media, comparative analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Each period is distinguished by the predominance of one or another form of literature. The second half of the 20th century is a new field of speech use, the rapid growth of mass communication. The rapid development of traditional mass media: print publications, radio, television, the emergence of new computer information technologies, the globalization of the world information space - all this did not affect the production process and the spread of the word. Media texts or media texts are one of the most common forms of language availability today.[1]

Media texts in English occupy a special place in the global information flow. Due to a number of political, economic and socio-cultural reasons, the total volume of media texts in English significantly exceeds the volume of media texts in other languages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The term "medialinguistics" was formed by analogy with a number of similar lexical units used to name new academic disciplines that appear at the intersection of sciences - sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, media psychology, media economics, etc. The term "medialinguistics" appeared in Russian scientific usage relatively recently, in 2000. It was used for the first time in T.G. Dobrosklonskaya's doctoral thesis "Theory and methods of media linguistics" [2], A little earlier its English version "media linguistics" appeared, which can be found in the works of British researchers.

The subject of this new science is the study of the activity of language in the field of mass communication, based on the term itself, which combines "mass media" (mass media) and "linguistics". That is, medialinguistics deals with a comprehensive study of a certain area of speech use - the language of mass media. The legitimacy of emphasizing media linguistics as a new direction of linguistics is connected with the huge role that mass media play for society and the individual. Most of the modern speech practices are used in the field of mass communication. The continuous improvement of information and communication technologies (ICT) leads to a steady increase in the total volume of texts distributed in different national languages in the global information space. At the same time, the subject of media linguistics is not the only discipline that has become a specific field of speech use: the same principle is used to separate another new field of linguistic research - political linguistics into an independent discipline. its study is the activity of the language in the field of political relations.[3]

RESULT

The study of various aspects of the use of speech in the rapidly developing field of mass communication not only led to the formation of the concept of "media language", but also served the formation of a new direction in modern linguistics - mediallynguistics. The subject of media linguistics comprehensively studies the functioning of language in the field of mass communication, or "the word in mass media". Within media linguistics, all previously disparate studies of various aspects of media discourse have been combined into a single systematic framework.[4]

The internal structure of media linguistics reflects a holistic view of the subject. All components and levels of mass media texts are deeply analyzed in a combination of linguistic and extralinguistic factors: the influence of the methods of creation and distribution of media texts on their linguistic and format features, functional-genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic issues and stylistic features, interpretation features, cultural features, ideological modality, pragmalinguistic value.

The main theoretical basis of media linguistics is the concept of media text, in which media text is considered as a dialectical unity of linguistic and media features representing a multi-layered, multi-level phenomenon. The main levels of media discourse include the spoken text level, the video sequence or graphic image level, and the audio accompaniment level. This is understood as diversity.

DISCUSSION

For media linguistics, the author is important as a unique person, his views, social status. Taking into account the experience of researchers, we prefer to work with the concept of "authorship" within the framework of the school of mediallynguistics.

Carrying out a comparative analysis, it should be said that the ways of expressing modality in English, regardless of the stylistic features of the text, are characterized by a special accuracy related to the semantic potential of the system of modal verbs. English modal verbs are a group of verbs that refer to an action rather than to the action itself. Therefore, Russian equivalents of modal verbs in English are often found in the group of predicates of the type can, need, required, and there is also a semantic similarity of English modal predicates with Uzbek adverbs and adverbial phrases, maybe, perhaps, should be, must, etc.; eg: That surplus has to be invested somewhere, and while Manchester City might be attractive, there aren't enough football clubs to go around. "This surplus should be invested somewhere, and although Manchester City is attractive, there are not enough football clubs for everyone.[6]

At the same time, it should be noted that the use of English modal verbs from these Uzbek equivalents corresponds to the technique of not naming the subject. But it is quite possible to translate English modal structures into Uzbek equivalent modal verbs and indicative mood verbs. Thus, in general, despite the typological differences between the Uzbek and English languages, the common conceptual meaning has been preserved.[5,6]

CONCLUSION In conclusion, it should be noted that mediallynguistics is a science that studies the activity of language in the media sphere, which appeared relatively recently. It was created at the intersection of two disciplines, so it has its own characteristics: on the one hand, it uses the base of linguistic research, and on the other hand, it is included in the general system of medialogy. media studies. Its main category is the media text, which is a complex and complex phenomenon that combines a number of characteristic features

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